

ISic3080

I.Sicily inscription 3080

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

monogram

Material

volcanic

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Naxos

Place of origin (modern)

Giardini-Naxos

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Giardini-Naxos

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI331820

1. ²unresolved monogram²

2.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645432

PHI 331820

Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 38.0954

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità*. At 276 fig.20

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